

Off-campus Performance of Student Teachers

Dr. Alexis Arizabal- Enriquez

Associate Professor, Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology, Bangued, Abra-Philippines. Email: aenriquez@asist.edu.ph

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.0000000

ABSTRACT

The paper looked into off-campus student teaching of the BSEd and BEEd student teachers using the descriptive approach in research, it identified their performance along with the parts of the lesson plan, classroom management, and assessment. There were 120 cooperating teachers who served as respondents in this study. Results showed that along with displaying professionalism, BSEd student teachers performed "Very Satisfactory" while "Outstanding" for BEEd. The BEEd student teachers performed better in lesson planning and items on personality. The student teachers need to improve in certain areas on classroom management, their art of questioning, how they motivate the class, and assessment. It is then recommended to conduct lectures, symposia, and fora where the student teachers displayed the lowest. Continuous support of the CTE pre-service program and activities to produce globally competitive prospected teachers and an interface with other Institutions to determine good and healthy off-campus practices and experiences of student teachers are encouraged.

Keywords: Pre-service Teachers, Bachelor of Secondary Education, Bachelor of Elementary Education, Professionalism, Managing and Motivating Class, Students' Performance

Cite as: Enriquez, Alexis (2022). OFF-CAMPUS PERFORMANCE OF STUDENT TEACHERS *LC International Journal of STEM* Volume. 3 No. (1), XX– XX. DOI: 0000-0001-8816-3792

INTRODUCTION

In order to remain globally competitive, education in the Philippines focuses on students' needs and provides holistic services to them. The Philippines must educate students who are capable of competing internationally. Teachers play a critical role in helping the country reach this goal by providing high-quality education. Their success, however, is contingent on skilled, knowledgeable teachers. For self-actualization and self-fulfillment to be feasible, the teacher's personal and professional attributes are a necessary condition of a facilitative and nurturing learning environment. To obtain good educational achievements, each school must focus on superiority and quality among teachers because quality instruction and monitoring are the foundations of a good education.

The Commission on Higher Education in 2004 rationalizes the pre-service teacher education to keep in stride with the demands globally. Pre-service teacher education is an important aspect of promoting high-quality education in the Philippines. Higher education institutions have been entrusted with a critical function and obligation. Pre-service teachers must prepare for and perform numerous tasks and functions of genuine teachers to improve the quality of education. As a result, the highest standards must be set while developing the pre-service education curriculum's objectives, components, and processes. Pre-service teachers must be equipped with the skills necessary to face the obstacles that

the job demands. They observe instructors in the classroom and focus on their abilities, methods, and classroom management. Their teaching experiences are assessed through conferences, and feedback is given to make real changes. Pre-service teachers receive valuable skills such as managing and analyzing class work, maintaining discipline, discovering their style, and being familiar with school organization. The researcher believes that students see the realities of the profession during student teaching, based on the preceding claims and observations. In the school where they are deployed, whatever concepts and theories learned in school are put into effect. They can effectively elicit their potential and skills by adapting to a new environment and culture. Students require guidance as they encounter great problems in the field, allowing them to either love or despise instruction. They are frequently placed in uncooperative and worrying situations, unsure of their authority, and occasionally even without senior teachers who can be of great assistance.

The researcher has been a mentor at the tertiary level of the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology Bangued Campus for fifteen years; she has noticed tremendous behaviors of student teachers. For six years, the researcher worked as a collaborating teacher at Laboratory High School. She noticed that the majority of student teachers were passive in certain school activities, hesitant to pass preparations for the lesson, hard-headedness, control and managing the class, had low confidence, had poor writing on questions for examinations, nervousness in demo-teaching, and had anger-inducing manners like absenteeism, unpunctuality, deserting classes. Regardless, most of the peers are more upbeat.

The goal of this paper is to collect data that can be used to enhance student teachers' performance. The results of this study may also assist instructors in better guiding student teachers to be successful in their careers despite challenges including dealing with aggressive students, having few resources, and putting students' needs and interests first. Advising them on what to look for in effective classroom instruction, appropriate strategies to use with various types of students, and appropriate attitudes toward colleagues and school staff may also help student teachers understand the value of student teaching before entering the world of teaching. It enables them to share essential information on suitable exam design, successful methods and strategies, appropriate parent and colleague communication, and good classroom management. This study might help teachers in charge of supervision understand the significance of effective mentoring and oversight. Future teachers who receive excellent mentoring and oversight develop the necessary skills and potential, enabling them to overcome challenges in their line of work. Finally, by highlighting teachers' outstanding contributions to student teaching, administrators may be able to connect them with other institutions, which is praiseworthy.

Background

This study focused on the off-campus performance of pre-service teachers or student-teachers as to their skills in writing lesson plans and presenting them to students, the art of questioning, classroom management and how they motivate their classes, evaluating students' performances, personalities, and dealing with their peers and other aspects of professionalism. Since the promulgation of the Commission's Memorandum in 2004, pre-service teacher education plays a very vital role in endorsing quality education, hence institutions have been entrusted with a critical function and obligation. Pre-service teachers then must be prepared for and explore to perform tasks and functions of dedicated teachers to see the real world of teaching. Standards are set to develop them and aligned pre-service education curriculum's objectives, components, and processes. The study employed the descriptive method of research for BEd and BSEd Graduating students who served as the respondents of this study. The researcher administered a questionnaire to measure the performance of the Student Teachers or pre-service teachers during their deployment on Lesson Planning, b. Organizing and Presenting Instruction, c. Questioning Skills, d. Managing and Motivating the Class, e. Assessing Students' Performance, f. Displaying Professionalism, and g. Personality, and a checklist for the profile of the

120 Cooperating Teachers. These students were deployed in various secondary and elementary, public and private schools from the 27 municipalities of the province of Abra.

In terms of physical, social, and leadership skills, Pinol (2000) discovered that academic achievement was unrelated to teaching responsibilities. She recommended that the College of Teacher Education enhance faculty by offering courses and/or seminars on instructional skills development in lesson planning, test construction, behavioral target setting, application of instructional strategies, and value formation. It may be encouraged to conduct ongoing research to pinpoint student teaching activities for better performance, curriculum review, early observation, and involvement in third-year college.

Teachers, according to Zehm (1993), have "charisma" to help individuals shine through their subject matter and seize the classroom's attention. Teachers and students agree on the atmosphere to develop a suitable, authentic, and appealing communication style. Students love professors who are genuinely caring and compassionate toward them to participate fully in class, he continued. The best instructors are more than just subject matter specialists or even entertaining people; they are persons that students can rely on because the best instructors are secure and compassionate. Even when they are not feeling well, have challenging assignments to do, or are required to teach relatively dull courses, they try their best. The accomplishment of the school's goals and objectives greatly influences every aspect of its operations. Employee satisfaction at work and provision of basic needs, including the motivation to persevere, might help achieve this. Working environment, interpersonal relationships, recognition of performance, and, well, a reasonable proportional compensation are some of the key criteria that motivate teachers to work more to attain goals and objectives. Teachers' performance determines whether the program succeeds or fails. They surely demonstrate great professionalism and teaching performance when given the correct motivation. Relationships with coworkers, pupils, and community members improve. They develop into responsible and accountable workers who uphold the greatest ethical standards in their tasks and functions, as well as altruistic individuals who help others.

The BEED student teachers displayed better than BSED pre-service students on lesson planning, questioning skills, assessing students' performances, managing and motivating the class, and personality. However, BSED student-teachers performed better in displaying professionalism, while both groups displayed well along with organizing and presenting instruction. These results were attributed to the mentoring executed by their respective cooperating teachers in various cooperating schools, intensive supervision of their supervising instructors, appropriate exposure to school tasks, a healthy environment in the cooperating schools, and good relationships between teachers and peers.

Objectives of the study

This study identified the off-campus performance of the prospective teachers along:

- a. Lesson Planning,
- b. Organizing and Presenting Instruction,
- c. Questioning Skills,
- d. Managing and Motivating the Class,
- e. Assessing Students' Performance,
- f. Displaying Professionalism, and
- g. Personality

Further, it described which of the items in the above-mentioned categories served lowest and highest performance of the respondents.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Background Theory

As stipulated in the Commission on Higher Education in 2004 that promoted pre-service teacher education to be abreast with the demands of times. CHED believes that the Philippines can be globally competitive through the teaching profession. Hence, pre-service teacher education becomes an important step toward promoting high-quality education in the Philippines. They then need to be well equipped with the skills and knowledge to perform numerous functions with genuine teachers. As a result, the highest standards must be set while developing the pre-service education curriculum's objectives, components, and processes. Pre-service teachers must be equipped with the skills necessary to face the obstacles that the job demands. They observe instructors in the classroom and focus on their abilities, methods, and classroom management. Their teaching experiences are assessed through conferences, and feedback is given to make real changes. Pre-service teachers receive valuable skills such as managing and analyzing class work, maintaining discipline, discovering their style and being familiar with school organization.

The researcher believes that students see the realities of the profession during student teaching, based on the preceding claims and observations. In the school where they are deployed, whatever concepts and theories learned in school are put into effect. They can effectively elicit their potential and skills by adapting to a new environment and culture. Students require guidance as they encounter great problems in the field, allowing them to either love or despise instruction. They are frequently placed in uncooperative and worrying situations, unsure of their authority, and occasionally even without senior teachers who can be of great assistance.

Previous Studies

Martinez (2004) reminded everyone that any organization's success is dependent on the interaction between and among its professionals. A successful school enables teachers and administrators to work together. Teachers' attitudes toward their careers and students are influenced by their colleagues' support and contact. The nature of interactions between and among professionals in a school setting is referred to as school collegiality. This has an impact on teachers' motivation and career commitment and willingness to change classroom practices. An interconnected school atmosphere is one in which teachers may collaborate effectively with peers and administrators, resolve conflicts with teachers, administrators, parents, and students, and match their talents and preferences.

As a result of the development of modern technology, aspiring teachers must learn how to use teaching resources in their classes. The most well-known technology is the computer. The use of ICT by pre-service teachers to raise student achievement was studied by Bihag (2011). To confirm its validity and gauge the extent of Cebu Normal University's implementation, integration, and practices, the experiment lasted two years. The students' portfolios showed that some of them were excellent and others were only fair. A less than impressive portfolio was produced as a result of the lack of resources for students to improve their ideas. The students were capable of achieving this, but because the majority of them were in school, they did not have the time to develop their work.

Further, Gautam (2005), a Professor in Tribhuvan University, USA wrote an article about "Practice Teaching: A Reflection- Practice/ Student Teaching: A Learning Experience or a Meaningless Ritual?" discussed the relevance of practice teaching and observed how the practice teachers see practice teaching as a part of their course. Teachers noted that the practice teachers go to school just for formality and they did not take the practice very seriously and that the practice teaching has not been very useful for the students as it was not being carried out as it should be. If this was true, this would have a very adverse effect not only on the school teaching system but also have a negative impact in the life of the practice teachers. To find out the current state of student teaching he made an accidental sampling approach. He visited the campus in the morning and stayed in the department and found out that large classes did not allow room for practice, the majority of the students did not want to practice their skills on the campus, and no appropriate environment was created on the campus, the faculty and student teachers were not very active in doing things rather they felt comfortable to the usual lecture

method, carelessness, and irregularity on the part of the student was also a main reason, and the faculty members confessed that they were not prepared enough to shift their role from a teacher to facilitator.

Conceptual Framework

The research paradigm revolves around the performance off-campus of pre-service teachers as assessed by their cooperating teachers in various areas parts of the lesson plan (LP), how they present and organize instruction, the art of questioning, managing the class, how to organizing and presenting instruction, c) questioning skills, d) managing and motivating the class, e) assessing the students' performance, f) displaying professionalism, and g) personality was also considered in this study.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed the descriptive method of research for BEd and BSEd Graduating students who served as the respondents of this study. The researcher administered a questionnaire to

measure the performance of the Student Teachers during their deployment on Lesson Planning, b. Organizing and Presenting Instruction, c. Questioning Skills, d. Managing and Motivating the Class, e. Assessing Students' Performance, f. Displaying Professionalism, and g. Personality, and a checklist for the profile of the Cooperating Teachers.

Data

The data collected came from the 120 cooperating teachers who observed 36 BSEd student teachers and 84 BEEd student teachers from the Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology Bangued Campus.

Method

The study employed the descriptive method of research for BEEd and BSEd Graduating students who served as the respondents of the 120 cooperating teachers. The researcher administered a questionnaire to measure the performance of the Student Teachers during their deployment on a. Lesson Planning(8 items), b. Organizing and Presenting Instruction (13 items), c. Questioning Skills(10 items), d. Managing and Motivating the Class(12 items), e. Assessing Students' Performance (8 items), f. Displaying Professionalism (10 items), and g. Personality (7 items). The rubrics below were used.

<u>Range of Scores</u>	<u>Item Descriptive Rating</u>	<u>Overall Descriptive Rating</u>
4.21 – 5.00	Very Strongly Demonstrated(VSD)	Outstanding (O)
3.41 – 4.20	Strongly Demonstrated (SD)	Very Satisfactory (VS)
2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Demonstrated (MD)	Satisfactory (S)
1.81 – 2.60	Slightly Demonstrated (SID)	Poor (P)
1.00 – 1.80	Not at All Demonstrated (NAD)	Needs Improvement (NI)

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results

Table 1
Level of Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents along with Lesson Planning

ITEMS	BSED		BEEED	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The lesson plan				
1.is readily available and is approved by the cooperating teacher before execution	4.25	VSD	4.61	VSD
2.is well designed and contains all essential parts(objectives, materials, procedures, assessment)	4.27	VSD	4.66	VSD
3.is well prepared	4.00	SD	4.58	VSD

4.shows consistent alignment of objectives, strategies, procedures, and assessments with standards	4.30	VSD	4.61	VSD
5.reflects meaningful choices of content	4.00	SD	4.48	VSD
6.contains the necessary information that students supposed to learn	4.08	SD	4.57	VSD
7.includes follow-up activities that enrich or extend the lesson	4.11	SD	4.44	VSD
8.is neat and free from typographical and grammatical errors	3.91	SD	4.30	VSD
<i>Total</i>	4.12	VS	4.53	O

Table 1 describes that as a whole, the BEEd student teachers performed “Outstanding” ($\bar{x} = 4.53$) while BSEd student teachers had $\bar{x}=4.12$. Yet, when taken singly, both student teachers performed item 2 “*is well designed and contains all essential parts (objectives, materials, procedures, assessment)*” as their highest, BEEd ($\bar{x} = 4.27$, VSD) and BSEd ($\bar{x} = 4.66$). Item 8 “*is neat and free from typographical and grammatical errors*”, BSEd ($\bar{x} = 3.91$, SD) and BEEd ($\bar{x} = 4.30$, VSD) as their lowest.

The “Outstanding” performance of the student teachers implies that they planned their lessons well before execution and indicated essential aspects for student learning and students’ needs.

Table 2
Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents
along Organizing and Presenting Instruction

ITEMS	BSED		BEED	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The student teacher				
1.establishes and maintains effective classroom routines (i.e., attendance, record keeping, etc.)	4.16	SD	4.32	VSD
2.demonstrates effective communication skills	3.86	SD	4.17	SD
3.relates lesson to actual life situations	3.86	SD	4.21	VSD
4.teaches in a creative, engaging, and appropriate manner	4.05	SD	4.27	VSD
5.engages students in thinking and problem solving activities	3.77	SD	4.13	SD

6.presents information with poise and confidence	4.02	SD	4.29	VSD
7.ensures a variety of teaching aids and materials like charts, graphs, flashcards, maps, globe, etc.	3.94	SD	4.54	VSD
8.uses relevant and responsive materials that are evident in every lesson	3.97	SD	4.34	VSD
9.demonstrates non-threatening atmosphere	4.19	SD	4.25	VSD
10.provides instruction that is appropriate for varied needs and styles of learners	4.16	SD	4.22	VSD
11.utilizes technology like computer, projector, films, etc., as teaching tools	3.08	SD	3.29	SD
12.summarizes the lesson/s of the day properly	4.00	SD	4.19	SD
13.maximizes interaction not only between teacher and students but also among students	4.25	VSD	4.23	VSD
<i>Total</i>	3.95	VS	4.19	VS

The table declares that as a whole, the student teachers performed “Very Satisfactory”, BSEd, (\bar{x} = 3.95) while BEEd (\bar{x} = 4.19).

When taken singly, the BSEd student teachers performed their highest in item 13, “*maximizes interaction not only between teacher and students but also among students*” (\bar{x} = 4.25) while the BEEd student teachers had their highest performance in item 9 “*which demonstrates a non-threatening atmosphere*” (\bar{x} = 4.25).

The results imply that the student teachers provided an environment for students to express and relate themselves with others freely.

The student-teachers performed the lowest in item 11, “*utilizes technology like computer, projector, films, etc., as teaching tools*”, BSEd (\bar{x} = 3.08) while BEEd (\bar{x} = 3.29).

This is attributed to the lack of confidence in the use of technologies and the availability of such modern technologies in the area where the student teachers were deployed.

Table 3
The Level of BSEd Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents along with Questioning Skills

ITEMS	BSED		BEED	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The student teacher				
1.explores learners' Understanding	3.72	SD	4.27	VSD
2.helps students articulate their ideas and thinking skills	3.77	SD	4.10	SD
3.give students “ think time” after posing questions	4.02	SD	4.16	SD

4.promotes risk-taking and problem solving	3.86	SD	3.85	SD
5.facilitates factual recall	4.08	SD	4.03	SD
6.encourages convergent and divergent thinking	3.77	SD	4.00	SD
7.stimulates curiosity	4.00	SD	4.03	SD
8.helps students to ask questions	3.86	SD	3.95	SD
9.rephrases questions which students find difficulty to answer	4.13	SD	3.94	SD
10.distributes questions for equal opportunity among pupils to answer	4.13	SD	4.22	VSD
<i>Total</i>	3.94	VS	4.05	VS

The BSEd student teachers performed highest in item 9 “*rephrases questions which students find difficulty to answer*” and item 10 “*distributes questions for equal opportunity among pupils to answer*” rated as “Strongly Demonstrated” (\bar{x} =4.13). They executed the lowest in item 1 which states “*explores learners’ understanding*” (\bar{x} = 3.72, SD). Yet, this item served as the highest for the BEEd (\bar{x} = 4.27, VSD). The BEEd student teachers executed the lowest in item 4, “*promotes risk-taking and problem-solving*” (\bar{x} = 3.85) rated as “Strongly Demonstrated”.

The student-teachers performed “Very Satisfactory”, BSEd (\bar{x} = 3.94) and BEEd (\bar{x} =4.05). The results show that the pre-service teachers assisted their students in understanding their lessons, and maximized student’s participation during discussions, but still needed to improve the ability to probe critical thinking.

Table 4
Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents along Managing and Motivating the Class

ITEMS	BSEd		BEEd	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The student teacher				
1.offers specific feedback to students about behavior	4.19	SD	4.00	SD
2.demonstrates consistent support and encouragement to students	4.08	SD	4.29	VSD
3.displays sound and affective traits such as caring, fairness,, respect, and socially interacts with students enthusiastically	4.11	SD	4.28	VSD
4.ensures that, when appropriate, student management issues are addressed and provides resources quickly	4.19	SD	4.14	SD
5.sets clear expectations for students	3.75	SD	4.09	SD
6.determines disciplines strategies that are appropriate	3.80	SD	4.15	SD

for age, individual, and school policies				
7.uses a variety of appropriate motivational techniques	3.86	SD	4.16	SD
8.provides a classroom and/ or laboratory that is safe for learning for all students	3.77	SD	4.19	SD
9.maintains clean and orderly classroom	3.86	SD	4.57	VSD
10.structures the classroom for possible re-arrangement of chairs and makes sure that the classroom is free from fixtures that distract students'	4.08	SD	4.41	VSD
11.involves the students in the design of rules and procedures in class	4.11	SD	4.17	SD
12.gives students consultation hours for personal discussions	3.97	SD	4.01	SD
<i>Total</i>	3.94	VS	4.20	VS

The table explains that as a whole, the BSEd student teachers performed “Very Satisfactory” (\bar{x} = 3.94) while the BEEd (\bar{x} = 4.20). When taken singly, the BSEd student teachers performed their highest in item 1, “offers specific feedback to students about behavior” and item 4, “ensures that, when appropriate, student management issues are addressed and provides resources quickly”, (\bar{x} = 4.19, SD). They had their lowest performance in item 5, “sets clear expectations for students” (\bar{x} = 3.75, SD). As for the BEEd student teachers, they performed their highest in item 9, “maintains clean and orderly classroom” (\bar{x} = 4.57, VSD), but performed the lowest in item 1, “offers specific feedback to students about behavior” (\bar{x} = 4.00, SD).

The results show that the student teachers upheld cleanliness and orderliness to promote healthy environment conducive for the students’ learning, resourceful, and managed students’ behavior in class. Yet, the student teachers need to be addressed on setting expectations, targets, and goals on their students.

Table 5
Level of Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents
along with Assessing Students’ Performance

ITEMS	BSED		BEED	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The student teacher				
1.monitors and provides feedback to students throughout the lesson	3.72	SD	4.11	SD
2.utilizes, when appropriate, pre- and post- assessments for student growth and improvement	3.75	SD	4.05	SD
3.utilizes a variety of assessment strategies throughout instruction and bases assessments on course goals/ objectives and standard	3.55	SD	4.07	SD

4.develops lesson plans to address remediation in order to extend learning of students	3.83	SD	4.19	SD
5.diagnoses learner's needs	3.69	SD	4.11	SD
6.evaluates learning outcomes	3.86	SD	4.20	SD
7.returns promptly results of examinations, assignments, projects, etc., to students for progress check	3.91	SD	4.20	SD
8.includes constructive guidance on how students can improve	3.83	SD	4.07	SD
<i>Total</i>	3.78	VS	4.12	VS

The table clearly states that as a whole, the student teachers performed “Very Satisfactory” BSEd, (\bar{x} =3.78) and the BEEd (\bar{x} = 4.12). When taken singly, the BSEd student teachers performed their highest in item 7, “*returns promptly results of examinations, assignments, projects, etc., to students for progress check*” (\bar{x} = 3.91, SD) while their lowest was at item 3, “*utilizes a variety of assessment strategies throughout instruction and bases assessments on course goals/ objectives and standard*” (\bar{x} = 3.55, SD). As for the BEEd student teachers, they had their highest in item 6, “*evaluates learning outcomes*” and item 7, “*returns promptly results of examinations, assignments, projects, etc., to students for progress check*” (\bar{x} = 4.20, SD) but they displayed their lowest in item 2, “*utilizes, when appropriate, pre-and post-assessments for student growth and improvement*” (\bar{x} = 4.05, SD).

These results show that the student teachers evaluated their students’ outputs and reported feedback to their students at once for self-monitoring, yet they need to improve on different assessment strategies to measure students’ progress.

Table 6
Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents
along Displaying Professionalism

ITEMS	BSED		BEEB	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
The student-teacher				
1.is reliable and punctual	4.05	SD	4.39	VSD
2. demonstrates initiative and assumes responsibility	4.08	SD	4.46	VSD
3.demonstrates high standards of moral and ethical behavior	4.16	SD	4.48	VSD
4.responds to diverse learners’ needs	4.02	SD	4.29	VSD
5.plans and works effectively with colleagues	4.19	SD	4.51	VSD
6.adheres to professional expectations for dress code and good grooming	4.11	SD	4.60	VSD
7.maintains positive parent communication	3.83	SD	4.34	VSD

8.maintains encouraging teacher- pupil and pupil-pupil communication	4.05	SD	4.30	VSD
9.continually strives to improve	4.22	VSD	4.45	VSD
10.creates and maintains contracts with peers from other institutions and other professional organizations for professional advancements	3.97	SD	4.32	VSD
<i>Total</i>	4.07	VS	4.41	O

As a whole, the BSEd student teachers performed “Very Satisfactory” ($\bar{x}=4.07$) while “Outstanding” for the BEEd ($\bar{x}= 4.41$). When taken singly, BSEd pre-service teachers performed highest in item 9, “*continually strives to improve*” ($\bar{x}= 4.22$, VSD) while lowest was in item 7, “*maintains positive parent communication*” ($\bar{x}=3.83$, SD). For the BEEd student teachers, they performed their highest in item 6, “*adheres to professional expectations for dress code and good grooming*” ($\bar{x}= 4.60$, VSD) while their lowest was in item 8, “*maintains encouraging teacher- pupil and pupil-pupil communication*” ($\bar{x}= 4.30$, VSD).

It only proves that the student teachers were prim and proper and displayed the appropriate grooming in their respective areas of deployment. On the other hand, the student teachers need to enhance proper communication with parents and students.

Table 7
Off-Campus Performance of the Respondents along with Personality

ITEMS	BSED		BEED	
	\bar{x}	DR		
The student teacher				
1.displays neatness and good grooming	4.63	VSD	4.82	VSD
2.is free from mannerisms that tend to disturb or distract students’ attention	4.11	SD	4.51	VSD
3.commands respect from the students	4.33	VSD	4.61	VSD
4.shows dynamism and enthusiasm	4.13	SD	4.59	VSD
5.observes well-modulated voice, when necessary	4.16	SD	4.53	VSD
6.displays courtesy at all times	4.22	VSD	4.66	VSD
7.exhibits obedience and respect to persons in authority	4.36	VSD	4.76	VSD
<i>Total</i>	4.28	O	4.73	O

As a whole, the student teachers performed “Outstanding” in this area, BSEd ($\bar{x}=4.28$) and BEEd ($\bar{x}=4.73$). Both groups had their highest performance in item 1, “*displays neatness and good grooming*”, BSEd ($\bar{x}=4.63$) and BEEd ($\bar{x}=4.82$). Yet, their lowest was in item 2, “*is free from mannerisms that tend to disturb or distract students’ attention*” BSEd ($\bar{x}=4.11$) and BEEd ($\bar{x}=4.51$).

This implies that the student teachers were presentable enough and displayed proper grooming to instigate respect from their students, but still needed to improve their confidence in teaching.

Table 8
Summary Performance of BSEd and BEEd
Student Teachers

ITEMS	BSEd		BEEd	
	\bar{x}	DR	\bar{x}	DR
A.Lesson Planning	4.12	VS	4.53	O
B.Organizing and Presenting Instruction	3.95	VS	4.19	VS
C.Questioning Skills	3.94	VS	4.05	VS
D.Managing and Motivating the Class	3.94	VS	4.20	VS
E.Assessing Students’ Performance	3.78	VS	4.12	VS
F.Displaying Professionalism	4.07	VS	4.41	O
G.Personality	4.28	O	4.73	O
OVERALL	4.01	VS	4.32	O

On the overall, the BEEd student teachers performed “Outstanding” ($\bar{x}=4.32$) while the BSEd student teachers performed “Very Satisfactory” ($\bar{x}=4.01$). Results were attributed to the better exposures of BEEd pre-service teachers than BSEd students during their off-campus student teaching, better monitoring, and better mentoring by their respective cooperating teachers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions:

1. The BEEd student teachers performed better in Lesson Planning, Displaying Professionalism, and Personality. These results are attributed to the apt exposures, mentoring, and monitoring delivered to them.
2. The BEEd and BSEd student teachers need to improve in certain areas like Organizing and Presenting Instruction, Questioning Skills, Managing and Motivating the Class, and Assessing Students’ Performance.

Recommendation

1. Conduct lectures, symposia, and forums on the areas where the student teachers displayed the lowest. These areas include the following: Organizing and Presenting Instruction, Questioning Skills, Managing and Motivating the Class, and Assessing Students’ Performance.
2. Continuous support of the CTE student teaching program and activities to produce globally competitive prospected teachers.
3. An interface with other Institutions to determine good and healthy off-campus practices and experiences of student teachers.

REFERENCES

Books

1. Arends, Richard I. (2000). *Learning to Teach. 5th Edition*. New York: Mc Graw-Hill Higher Education.
2. Corpuz, Brenda B. (2007). *Facilitating Learning: A Metacognitive Process*. Quezon City: Lorimar Publishing Inc.
3. DECS Manual
4. Martinez, Mario, C. (2004). *Teachers Working Together for School Success*. California: Corwin Press.
5. Oakes, Jeannie, et. al. (2007). *Teaching to Change the World. 3rd Edition*. New York: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
6. Ornstein, Allan. (2003). *Contemporary Issues in Curriculum. 3rd Edition*. USA: Pearson Education, Inc.
7. Zehm, Stanley, J., et. al. (1993). *On Being a Teacher, the Human Dimension*. California: Corwin Press.

Unpublished Theses and Dissertations

1. De Peralta, Rosa R. (1990). *Motivation, Self- Concept, and Other Personal Factors as Related to Academic Achievement among Student in State Colleges and Universities in Region I and the National Capital Region*. Dissertation. University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
2. Pinol, Gorgonia, N. (2000). *Determinants of BSE Student Teachers' Performance in SUCs of Region I and The National Capital Region*. Dissertation. University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.
3. Viernes, Norma, V. (2010). *Performance of the Graduates of Selected State Colleges and Universities of Solid North in the Licensure Examination for Teachers*. Dissertation. University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City.

Papers Presented during Conferences

1. 2012 International Conference on Education and Management Innovation. *Centers of Excellence and Centers of Development for Teacher Education: Their Contribution to the Elementary Teacher Force*. IPEDR Vol 30 (2012). Singapore: IACSIT Press.
2. Bihag, Helen L. (2011). *ICT Integration and Practices of the Pre-servic Teachers in Cebu Normal University (CNU)*. Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference of Teaching and Learning Intel. International University, Malaysia.
3. Lucas, M.R.D., et. al., *Validation of a Proposed NCBTS- Based Practice Teaching Manual*. Presented during the First National Teacher Education Research Congress. September 24-25, 2010, Cebu, City.

Electronic References

1. Bumatay, Ernesto L. et.al., http://www.usm.edu.ph/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=486%3Ainsights-from-practiceteachersandexperiences. *Insights from practice teaching experiences of student teachers.* (March 28, 2013).
2. Wagenaar, Melanie(2005). URI: <http://hdl.handle.net/10530/523>. *Student Teachers' Experiences of Practice Teaching.*
3. <http://anniejenningspr.com/jenningswire/success/become-a-practice-teacher/> . *Become a Practice Teacher.* (February 16, 2014).
4. Chickering and Ehrmann. *Implementing the Seven Principles: Technology as Lever.* <http://www.aahe.org/technology/ehrmann.htm>.
5. *Teacher Development Through Deliberate Practice* http://tntp.org/assets/tools/Deliberate_Practice_TNTP_6JUN2013.pdf
6. *Teacher/Leader Effectiveness* <http://www.engageny.org/teacherleader-effectiveness>
7. *The Benefits of Guided Practice Teaching* <http://tesoltrainers.blogspot.com/2013/03/the-sit-tesol-certificate-and-guided.html>
8. *Conducting Professionalism at Workplace.* <http://www.buzzle.com/articles/professionalism-in-the-workplace.html>.
9. *Tips for Professionalism: James Stenson.* http://www.ehow.com/way_5304458_tips-professionalism-workplace.html:
10. *8 reasons why should you join Student Organizations in US Universities? How many to Join ? What kind of student organizations to Join ?* <http://redbus2us.com/8-reasons-why-should-you-join-student-organizations-in-us-universities-how-many-to-join-what-kind-of-student-organizations-to-join/>
11. *The Scholarship Coach.* <http://www.usnews.com/education/blogs/the-scholarship-coach/2011/07/07/5-reasons-why-scholarships-are-essential>.

BIOGRAPHY

Dr. Alexis Arizabal-Enriquez is an Associate Professor 4 of The Abra State Institute of Sciences and Technology (Deemed-to-be University of Abra). She finished her Master of Arts in Teaching English and Doctor of Education in the University of Northern Philippines, Vigan City while her baccalaureate degree, AB English at The University of the East, Recto Manila.

Her various designations since 2004: *Technical Paper Adviser of The Technocrat* (2004-2011), *Director of Information and Publication* (2012-2014), *Dean of the College of Teacher Education* (2014- 2019) has tremendously taught her worthwhile experiences as she engaged with countless educators in the professional world. Awarded as **“Faculty Researcher in 2019 and 2020”** by her Institution, her skills and passion to explore in research paved the way for local, national, regional, and international presentations and vied as **“Best Presenter”**. Most of her researches have been published in International Refereed and Peer Reviewed Journals, and Scopus Indexed International Journals. She is also a reviewer of several international journals, served as judge in the national and international research presentations, speaker in various international webinars, appointed as regional Coordinator for ALOYSIAN PUBLICATION. She was awarded as **“Most Outstanding Research Advocate”** by Asia Pacific Awards Council on July 2020 and **“Best Research Paper”** in the 5th International Conference in Research, Education, Management, and Social Sciences (ICREMSS) via Zoom on December 12, 2021.

With her stance as an *Accreditor* of the Accrediting Agency of Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCUP), she has accredited several Universities and Colleges in the country. As an ISO 9001: 2015 *internal auditor (Over- all Coordinator)* of her school, she has ardently supported her school in various quality assurance endeavors and yielded the same sense in her delivery of quality education to her valued students.